

Complex Formation Equilibria of Acetohydroxamic Acid with H^+ and UO_2^{2+} Ion in Aqueous Organic Mixtures

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The present communication deals with pH-metric determination of proton-ligand stability constants of acetohydroxamic acid and stability constants of its uranyl complexes in aqueous, methanol-water, ethanol-water, isopropanol-water and dioxane-water mixtures keeping constant mole fraction of organic solvents.

Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand stability constant ($\log K_1^{H^+}$) corresponding to the ionisation of hydroxyl proton from NHOH group of the ligand were calculated from n_A vs pH data in the pH range 8–11 by Irving-Rossotti method¹ (Table 1).

Wise and Brandt² reported $\log K_1^{H^+}$ 9.4 while Schwarzenbach and Schwarzenbach³ reported 9.37 for acetohydroxamic acid in aqueous solution and which are in close agreement with the present values of $\log K_1^{H^+}$ in aqueous solution. Values of n were calculated for uranyl-acetohydroxamic acid in the pH range 4.2–6.3,

4.0–5.9, 4.0–6.7, 4.0–6.5, 4.3–7.5 in water, methanol-water, ethanol-water, isopropanol-water and dioxane-water respectively, and the values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were calculated from n vs pL curves using various computational methods¹ (Table 1).

Considering the effect of dielectric constant (ϵ) at constant mole fraction of organic solvent on $\log K_1^{H^+}$ value in various aqueous organic mixtures, the results showed greater value of $\log K_1^{H^+}$ with increase in $1/\epsilon$. Here it should be noted that, as predicted by the Born⁴ equation, the creation of charge in media of low dielectric constants is an unfavourable process and hence resulting in greater $\log K_1^{H^+}$ values. The values of $\log K_1^{H^+}$ and $\log K_1$ followed the order: dioxane-water > isopropanol-water > ethanol-water > methanol-water > water, which is parallel to the order of increase in dielectric constants of the various solvents. It is commonly held that water molecules are preferentially, if

TABLE 1 – PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF ACETOHYDROXAMIC ACID AND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF ITS $UO_2^{H^+}$ COMPLEXES IN AQUEOUS/ORGANIC MIXTURES*

Temp. = 25°, $I = 0.15 M$ (NaCl)

Solvent composition %(v/v)	Mole fraction of organic solvent	$1/\epsilon$	$\log K_1^{H^+}$	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log K_1/\log K_2$
Aqueous (100%)	0.00	0.013 0	9.45	7.63	6.62	1.15
Methanol-water (42.5 : 57.5%)	0.24	0.016 7	10.05	8.46	7.40	1.14
Ethanol-water (51.8 : 48.2)	0.24	0.019 8	10.10	8.50	7.00	1.21
Isopropanol-water (58.6 : 41.4)	0.24	0.029 8	10.19	8.61	7.22	1.19
Dioxane-water (61.2 : 38.8)	0.24	0.039 9	10.85	8.67	6.83	1.27

*Standard deviations of values are +0.02 log units

not almost exclusively solvated in mixed solvent, and the importance of taking into account the elimination of coordinated water molecules as a cause contributing to the medium effect, has been reported⁵. Thus a reaction of complex formation may be described by the equation,

The increase in stability of ML ($\log K_1$) in an aqueous mixed solvent compared to that in water alone, derives in some part from the lower activity of water in the mixed solvent compared to this value in pure water. The sharp increase in $\log K_1$ value from water to methanol-water mixture followed by a gradual increase with increase in $1/\epsilon$ was observed. It has been reported⁶ that methanol molecules are capable of appreciable solvation from aqueous methanol solution. This solvation accounts for sharp increase in $\log K_1$ value in methanol-water mixture compared to only aqueous medium because the release of coordinated solvent molecules is favourable for enhanced stability of metal-ligand complex. The greater $\log K_1$ in mixed solvents suggests that the ion-ion interaction between the uranyl ion and the acetohydroxamic acid intensifies to a greater extent than the ion-dipole interaction between the metal ion and the solvent. However, the trend, dioxane-water > ethanol-water > isopropanol-water > methanol-water > water, was followed in case $\log K_1/\log K_2$ values (Table 1). This is because the order of dielectric constant (ϵ) of the solvent does not exactly follow the order of $\log K_2$ values. This may be explained on the basis of electrostatic and nonelectrostatic components of metal ligand bond. At mole fraction 0.24, structuredness⁷ of water crosses the maximum value of all the other media and it has its usual acidity upto approximately mole fraction 0.24 and ionic component of metal-ligand bond responds to the changes in $1/\epsilon$ in case of $\log K_1$ values. This suggests that formation of successive steps of complexation (ML and ML_2) are not influenced in a similar pattern by the change in dielectric constant. It is further observed that $\log K_2$ is considerably increased in methanol-water mixture while it increased slightly in dioxane-water mixture compared to aqueous medium. The expected response of $\log K_2$

to change in $1/\epsilon$ in dioxane-water mixture is not met and may indicate covalent nature of metal-ligand bonding in formation of ML_2 from ML.

Experimental

The purity of acetohydroxamic acid (*N*-hydroxyacetamide) (Sigma) was checked potentiometrically and its solution was prepared in distilled water. All other chemicals were either of A.R. grade or purified before use. Uranyl nitrate [$UO_2(NO_3)_2$] was B.D.H. product Bjerrum-Calvin^{8,9} pH-titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti¹⁰ was used for potentiometric determination of stability constants. The mole ratio of metal-to-ligand was kept at 1 : 5 in order to fulfil maximum coordination number of metal ions. Concentrations of reactants used were $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ HCl, $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand and $4 \times 10^{-4} M$ uranyl ion. Total volume in each case was 20 ml. An EC digital pH-meter with combined glass electrode assembly was used for pH-measurement in titrations against 0.1 N NaOH. The titration curves for acid, acid + ligand and acid + ligand + uranyl ion in aqueous organic mixtures were of usual shape.

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